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HumanTech News

HUMANTECH'S PROGRESS + UPDATES ON TECH,
SAFETY AND SUSTAINABILITY IN CONSTRUCTION

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Hello,

It has been a year since we started our journey! We are excited about what we have achieved and are very much looking forward to continuing to innovate, collaborate and work towards a better future for construction.

Before we dive into the stories, opportunities, resources and inspiration we bring you, let us share some of our latest developments during this time — **an incredible year of driving positive change in the building sector.**

Since HumanTech started, we have already seen our first promising results — from scanning and semantic reconstruction to wearables integration and robotics & perception — while we have begun our first round of user evaluations. In addition, the scientific excellence of our consortium is already evident with three publications and technical challenge awards. We have also been active in communication, dissemination and community building for AI in construction by organising two technical workshops with impressive attendance and strengthening our collaboration with other EU-funded projects.

Having invested a good amount of time in clearly defining tasks, dependencies and architectures, we will focus even more on our technical developments in digital building twins, construction wearables and robotics in the coming period.

We can not wait for what this next phase will bring!

[Learn more about our progress and next steps](#)

Join us in celebrating [#1YearofHumanTech!](#)

Now, let's dive into our updates, insightful stories, opportunities, resources and inspiration on construction innovation. Enjoy!

HumanTech Stories

[HumanTech wins 3rd place in the CV4AEC workshop's Scan-to-BIM challenge at CVPR 2023](#)

Our colleagues Jason Rambach and Mahdi Chamseddine, from the German Research Center for Artificial Intelligence (DFKI), and Fabian Kaufmann, from RPTU Kaiserslautern-Landau, have won the 3rd prize in the International Scan-to-BIM competition of the 'Computer Vision in the Built Environment' workshop at the CVPR 2023 conference.

[Human factors in construction robotics: Special session on the 19th IEEE ARSO Conference](#)

In June 6, we held a special session at the 19th IEEE International Conference on Advanced Robotics and Its Social Impacts (ARSO 2023), where we shared highlights of our ongoing research activities. Our colleagues from DFKI, SINTEF, BAuA, STAM and TECNALIA were present.

Next HumanTech events

Our partners at Naska.AI will participate in more events during July:

- **3 July, India:** [International Symposium on Automation and Robotics in Construction](#) (ISARC 2023), where they are organising a workshop on Point-Cloud processing and have a paper accepted.
- **6-7 July, Switzerland:** [AI for Good Global Summit](#), where they will display their robotic platform.

[Building the future: The benefits HumanTech technologies bring to construction workers](#)

At HumanTech, we are developing human-centred technology solutions that will facilitate the work of construction professionals — creating a safer, greener, more efficient and rewarding working environment. Find out how our technologies will positively impact construction workers day to day.

[Press Release: Standards Supporting Smarter and Greener Construction in Europe](#)

We have joined forces with StandICT.eu to foster standardisation for a smarter and greener European construction industry. We both share ambitions to contribute to future international standards on smart building and aim to leverage the established efforts in this field.

[We celebrate our 2nd Executive Board Meeting](#)

Our 2nd Executive Board Meeting was a perfect example of collaborative and efficient work to share our progress, align our goals, strategies and priorities, and coordinate our next actions to accelerate the green and digital transition of the European construction industry.

[AI and Robotics in Construction: HumanTech's first workshop at the ERF 2023](#)

We held our first workshop at the European Robotics Forum 2023 (ERF2023), where our team members shared their vision on AI and robotics's impact on the construction sector with around 100 attendees, who learned how we are creating a better building industry together with other public, industrial, and scientific organisations.

[Using motion capture technology to reduce workplace injuries in construction](#)

One of our main goals is to reduce workplace injuries by 30% in construction. Our partners at SINTEF are building on the motion-capture technology developed by Sci-Track to improve construction workers' safety and well-being and provide services for human-robot collaboration.

[HumanTech Publication: OPA-3D - Occlusion-Aware Pixel-Wise Aggregation for Monocular 3D Object Detection](#)

Dive into our first scientific publication, accepted in the IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters (RA-L) journal. Authors: our project coordinator Dr. Jason Rambach and experts Yongzhi Su, Yan Di, Fabian Manhardt, Guangyao Zhai, Benjamin Busam, Didier Stricker and Federico Tombari.

Meet the [#HumanTechTeam](#)

- [Hideaki Kanayama](#), Engineer at RICOH
- [Fernando Sigchos](#), European Builders Confederation (EBC) Secretary General
- [Implemia](#): Patrick Roth, Project Manager of New Business Models & Innovation, and Sebastian Mattes, BIM & Reality Capturing Specialist
- [Soungcho CHAE](#), Chief Research Engineer at Kajima Technical Research Institute Singapore (KaTRIS)
- [Marcus Miezal](#), CEO and Co-Founder of Sci-track
- [Arantxa Renteria](#), Projects Lead at TECNALIA
- [Rachele A. Bernardello](#), Phd Research Fellow in geometric and semantic modelling at the University of Padova
- [Anurag Bansal](#), Innovation Manager at ACCIONA's Construction Technology Center
- [Carina Pamminger](#), Chief Project Manager at Holo-Light
- [Patricia Rosen](#), Human Factors and Ergonomics scientist at the Federal Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (BAuA)
- [Francesca Canale](#), Project Engineer at STAM
- [Florendia Fourli](#), CEO and Managing Director of Hypercliq

Unlocking the Future of Research

We have started a new editorial series: "Unlocking the Future of Research". In it, our exceptional PhDs, PostDocs, junior researchers and colleagues will share their stories about what it's like to work on our project and how it can influence their careers.

Meet our first guest, [Chiara Zarna](#), a brilliant research scientist at SINTEF, driven by new challenges, the opportunity to collaborate with our international partners, gain international visibility and identify future research trends and needs.

Stay tuned for more captivating stories and insights from our researchers as we continue to unlock the future of research!

Tech4EUconstruction

#Tech4EUconstruction

We have joined forces with our sister projects, BEEYONDERS and RoBétArmé, to create the “Tech4EUconstruction” collaborative cluster. Together, our three EU-funded projects are boarding on an exciting journey to address key challenges of the European construction sector.

[Learn more about our cluster](#)

BEEYONDERS · [Robots for gender balance: helping women conquer the construction sector](#) | Women still struggle to break the glass ceiling of the construction industry. Discover how robots will tackle gender inequality, foster safety and save the industry from the “ticking bomb” of labour force shortage.

[RoBétArmé’s newsletter #2](#) | Discover the RoBétArmé Project’s latest updates and developments.

Beyond HumanTech

Opportunities to take action and inspiration from our sector.

Opportunities to Take Action

- The **STAND4EU project** is organising an interactive workshop to discuss promoting involvement in standardisation activities, standards management, and standardisation in additive manufacturing, intelligent manufacturing, circular economy and welding. [Join on June 30.](#)

- Join StandICT.eu, HSbooster.eu and STAND4E for the webinar “**Women in ICT Standards**”, focused on the gender gap in ICT standardisation and standards. They will discuss the current status of women's participation and contribution to standards & technical committees and activities in the ICT domain. [Join on July 4.](#)
- Our partners at the **European Builders Confederation** are celebrating their annual congress, dedicated to sustainability in construction with a focus on the current and potential role of construction SMEs & crafts. It will be held at The Hague, Netherlands, in a hybrid format. [Join on July 5.](#)
- Are you an ICT standardisation specialist? [Apply to StandICT.eu's open call up until 10 July](#), which allocates € 2,925,000 in funding to support European Standardisation experts working on ICT standards.

Inspiring resources

- [Building 4.0 CRC](#), an industry-led research initiative co-funded by the Australian Government which aims to develop an internationally competitive, dynamic and thriving Australian advanced manufacturing sector, delivering better buildings at lower cost and the human capacity to lead the future industry.
- [Exoskeletons: Will they become a more common sight on construction sites?](#) Musculoskeletal disorders (MSD) are the single largest cause of work-related illness in construction. Providing workers with a wearable solution that reduces strain on their joints during repetitive manual tasks and, in some cases, increases their strength, seems like an obvious step. A potential solution is the use of exoskeletons — discover some of the options available.
- Our partner, the Federal Institute for Materials Research and Testing (BAM), has recently contributed to a pre-print paper titled “**14 Examples of How LLMs Can Transform Materials Science and Chemistry: A Reflection on a Large Language Model Hackathon**”. The paper is available on [Arxiv](#), along with the code and

dataset on [GitHub](#) for BAM's contribution entitled Text2Concrete.

To finish, one last recommendation

[The Lean Construction Blog's Podcast, with Dick Bayer](#)

A podcast dedicated to stories, case studies and lessons learned of applying Lean Construction from around the world.

Thanks for reading,
The HumanTech Team

[Get in touch](#)

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WHO ARE WE?

The HumanTech Team

HumanTech is a Horizon Europe-funded project carried out by 22 partners from 10 countries with expertise in robotics, wearables, artificial intelligence and extended reality.

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für Angewandte Wissenschaften

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